

GREEN LOANS AND THE VULNERABILITY OF INDUSTRIES: THE CASE OF GEORGIA**Pavliashvili S.,***Doctor of economic sciences, Professor, Academician
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8249489>***Abstract**

The article states that "green finance" reflects the connection between environmental aspects and financial solutions and instruments that integrate humanitarian, ecological, technological, socio-political, and cultural issues.

The study differentiates risk-based green finance from economic and value-based green finance. It singles out the agricultural sectors, which are most exposed to climate risks and have an exceptionally high contribution to climate change.

The study examines how the vulnerability of industries to environmental risks affects lending to these industries by the financial sector. It is based on the heat map methodology and determines lending risks by the dimensions of acute, high-risk, and vulnerable-risk loans. In addition, the concept is taken as a priori, according to which the share of loans should reflect the riskiness of industries, including the environment.

The study compares five sectors—energy, agriculture, construction, industry, transport and communication—and the share of loans issued in these sectors in total assets and output. It is established that if the climate impact was not given an essential role in the activities of commercial banks in the financing of the economy, only in agriculture, the climate impact had an indirect influence on the lending decisions of the financial institutions.

Keywords: sustainable development, green finance, agriculture, climate impact, loans, risks.

Introduction

In today's world, the financial system's consideration of environmental and social responsibility issues is gaining particular relevance as one of the contributing factors to sustainable development. In this regard, participation in the capital market and green, social, and sustainable financing of social and environmental issues present new challenges. Financial risk management becomes critical because the management of financial resources for sustainable development depends not only on the financial management culture and investment decisions of companies but also on the consideration of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors and the management of state policies.

Methodological approaches

Sustainable financing and related financial risks are also connected to climate change, which has long-term effects on the economy and threatens financial stability by creating uncertainties.

There are many approaches to identifying risks to sustainable development in the economy. The assessments of risks by financial organizations and the determination of different degrees of their impact are mainly done through observation and analysis. To this end, they use different methodologies, especially the "top-down" approach, which involves determining the potential risks of the sector based on available data. Their empirical analysis assesses environmental, social, and governance (ESG) risks more generally. More emphasis is placed on acute and chronic natural-climatic risks, which are tangible and belong to high risks. These are mainly the risks related to the use of agricultural products and natural resources, according to which the vulnerability of this sector is determined. Research has

been conducted to manage the risk reduction (avoidance) process in determining the credit policy of commercial banks, which requires the identification, assessment, and mapping of risks.

Market volatility and environmental challenges create transitory, transformational, and physical risks. Under such threats, companies face economic problems that may harm their ability to repay loans to varying degrees and thus affect banks and financial stability in general.

The relationship between environmental aspects and financial solutions and instruments is commonly called "green finance" ("green investment," "climate finance," etc.). Protecting the stability of economic and financial systems from the influence of environmental risks can be called risk-based green finance while introducing the concepts of justice, morality, and ethics in business into the investment process (socially responsible investment, or SRI) is value-based green finance (1, p. 6).

The effectiveness of the legal framework significantly determines the efficacy of green finance, the country's technological capabilities, the level of demand for environmental measures in the market, the behaviors of consumers, the sociocultural environment, etc. are separate assessment areas that combine humanitarian, environmental, technological, socio-political, and cultural issues.

Case of Georgia

Georgia is rich in environmental resources, such as water, land, forests, and biodiversity. The global climate risk index ranks Georgia 108th among the most affected countries. The country exists in the field of extreme weather events, which means an obvious

danger (3, p.36). According to EU4Climate (4), Georgia is highly vulnerable to climate change and has acute physical climate risks due to the increased frequency and severity of floods and landslides. It causes significant damage to the economy (4).

According to the Climate Risk Country Profile compiled by the World Bank Group and the Asian Development Bank, Georgia is characterized by higher-than-average temperatures, severe droughts, and water shortages. In addition, the water supply through rivers is threatened due to shrinking glaciers. This leads to significant economic consequences (1).

Significant problems exist, particularly a need for environmental infrastructure and services. Humans and climate change induced environmental degradation, which decreased the natural resource base as an essential source of local livelihoods and, thus, increased rural poverty, declining environmental quality, and public health and wellbeing. Degraded terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, modified river bodies, floodplain zones, forests, arable and pasture lands, deteriorated water and drainage systems, and soil quality. Lost economic assets and deteriorated livelihoods, thus hindering rural development. Moreover, enhanced climate-induced natural hazards

The biggest problems are the application of unsustainable environmental and natural resource management technologies and practices; limited or absent information and local knowledge and capacities on sustainable environment and integrated natural resource management; climate change adaptation and disaster risk management; renewable energy and energy efficiency; deteriorated or absent essential environmental and climate change adaptation and disaster risk management infrastructure; and poor access to environmental and climate change adaptation and disaster risk management financing.

Environmental pressures cause several problems, such as degraded terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, modified river bodies, floodplain zones, forests, arable and pasture lands, deteriorated water and soil quality, and enhanced climate-induced natural hazards (landslides, mudflows, rockfalls, and flash floods), which in turn reduce the quality of life of the local population, which faces several climate change problems and related consequences.

Sustainable Development Goals implementation

Georgia signed an Association Agreement with the European Union aimed at political association and economic integration. According to paragraph 301 of the Association Agreement, the parties will build and strengthen their relations, taking into account the long-term goals of sustainable development and a green economy, which, through the implementation of the interests of economic growth and environmental protection of society, will ensure human wellbeing, an increase in the quality of life, and the right of future generations to benefit from the natural environment protected as much as possible from changes in

resources and the environment and to meet the needs of the present without endangering future generations.²

It should be considered that damage to ecosystems and nature may result in the spread of fatal animal pathogens and diseases. A sharp increase in natural cataclysms caused by climate change is already visible. A country will need adequate capacity to tackle these global challenges and the significant environmental challenges addressed in the SDGs.

According to the Sustainable Development Report 2022, Georgia ranks 51st out of 163 countries in the ranking of the implementation/progress of sustainable development goals (14, p.210). Significant challenges are noted regarding carbon dioxide emissions (SDG-13, climate action). CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion and cement production (tCO₂/capita) amount to 2.5 (2020); CO₂ emissions embodied in imports (tCO₂/capita) are 0.6 (2018), and CO₂ emissions embodied in fossil fuel exports (kg/capita) - to 14.1 (2021). Georgia's long-term goal is to reduce them to zero.

Progress has yet to be made in improving solid waste collection, recycling, and nitrogen removal rates. There are challenges regarding waste and sulfur dioxide emissions (SDG 12—Responsible Consumption and Production). Environmental pollution from hazardous waste is a significant problem. In Georgia, electronic waste per capita is about 7.8 kg. Moreover, only 1 percent of electronic devices are made in Georgia, and 99 percent are imported. Georgia generates about 51-52 kg of waste per capita annually. As of 2020, in Georgia, as a result of the consumption of electronic devices, an average of 7.3 kilograms of waste were produced per capita (Pavliashvili S., etc. 2020). The goal of sustainable development is to reduce this indicator to 0.2 kg. Other indicators are municipal solid waste (kg/capita/day) value calculated at 0.5 (2015); electronic waste (kg/capita) at 7.3 (2019); production-based SO₂ emissions (kg/capita) at 4.8 (2018); SO₂ emissions embodied in imports (kg/capita) at 1.5 (2018); production-based nitrogen emissions (kg/capita) at 8.9 (2015); nitrogen emissions embodied in imports (kg/capita) at 3.1 (2015); and exports of plastic waste (kg/capita) at 0.2 (2021).

According to SDG 14 (Life Below Water) estimation, the mean area protected in marine sites important to biodiversity accounts for 35.6% of 2020; the Ocean Health Index: Clean Waters score (worst 0–100, best) is 55.2 %. (2020); Fish caught that are then discarded (2018: 8.1% (2018).

Life on Land indicators (SDG 15) show that critical are the following: the mean area that is protected in terrestrial sites important to biodiversity equals 40.3% (2020), and the mean area that is protected in freshwater places important to biodiversity is 38.9% (2020).

There is the following cause-and-effect chain for sustainable development: with development comes more and more intensive consumption of resources.

action plan aimed at intensifying efforts to address the contemporary global challenges facing the world, one of which is dealing with climate and environmental challenges (18).

² In September 2015, the UN General Assembly adopted the resolution "Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development", The resolution is a 15-year

There is a shortage of resources, and the issue of land, water, and raw material usage is becoming more acute. Controlling and managing natural resources is becoming more and more difficult. The problems are interrelated. The intensification of the use of resources requires an emphasis on environmental measures and a socially responsible attitude, which ultimately affects the course of climate change. The latter indicates how consistently and rationally sustainable development goals are being implemented.

Vulnerable sectors of Georgia

The sectors that are most affected by climate risks, have a high contribution to climate change and create exceptionally high risks include agriculture, forestry, fishing (perennial crop cultivation, forestry activities), food production, chemical and chemical product production, electricity, gas, steam, and air conditioning supply, water supply, sewerage, waste management, and remediation activities. High-risk sectors include perennial crop production, animal production (fishing and aquaculture), tobacco production, coke and refined petroleum product production, motor vehicle, trailer, and semi-trailer production, construction, transportation, and storage (2, p.14-18).

Globally, agriculture is the sector most affected by extreme weather events. On the other hand, in the world, 10 million hectares of forest are destroyed every year, and almost 90 percent of global deforestation is due to agricultural expansion (17). Agriculture is significantly dependent on the country's natural resources and ecosystem.

According to Georgia's national greenhouse gas inventory report, agriculture was characterized by the highest greenhouse gas emissions (about 20%) from 1990 to 2017 (7). The evaluation according to the taxonomy of the European Union is also similar (13, p.12).

One aspect of Georgia's 2030 Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan 2021-2023 is to support

measures to achieve low carbon in the agricultural sector (5). However, experts call for the measure to be more concrete and business-like (2, p.14-18).

Agricultural waste, water, and soil are the target objects of sustainable agriculture development. Agricultural activities pollute the air less. It affects environmental pollution in different ways. Vehicle emissions and the burning of agricultural waste mainly cause air pollution. Air emissions, surface and underground water pollution, and soil pollution are significant problems, especially in regions where agricultural production is developed. Georgia is distinguished by a very high intensity of energy and resource use. This indicator in Georgia is 2-2.5 times higher than the indicator in Western countries (12, p.296-320).

One of the widespread practices of environmental pollution is clearing agricultural areas of post-harvest residues using fire. Fire significantly affects the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil, its yield, and environmental factors. The degree of change caused by fire depends on the intensity and duration of the fire. The latter, in turn, depends on such circumstances as fuel type and amount, air temperature and humidity, soil characteristics in terms of moisture content, texture, organic matter, and above-ground biomass characteristics. The impact of fire on soil includes loss of soil organic matter, alteration of above-ground vegetation and topsoil biomass, destruction, increased soil erosion processes, which further negatively affect soil organic matter and water-holding capacity, and other changes resulting from crop residue burning. As a result of the mentioned activity, the windbreak near the seats was destroyed. Farmers burn 27–29 percent of the soil every year. 25 percent of farmers claim that fires started by neighboring farmers damage them. Thus, approximately 40 percent of agricultural land is burned regularly.

Graph 1-2

The average percentage of burning of cultivated fields by farmers in order to clean them from agricultural residues

Source: Pavliashvili S., Gubeladze D. Agriculture, Economic Performance Management and Circular Economy. Tb. 2020, p. 291-292. (In Georgian).

The use of agricultural technologies that are less harmful to the environment is an effective means of reducing the negative impact of agricultural waste on the environment, including compliance with the doses, terms, and rules of the use of pesticides and agrochemicals; use of biological methods of protecting plants from harmful organisms and diseases; replacement of herbicides and pesticides with bio stimulators; introduction of integrated processes of soil protection; introduction of manure management; integrated management of pastures; correct management of biological waste from livestock; measures to reduce soil salinization; etc.

Some other directions for implementing green economy principles in agriculture include: ensuring ecologically clean agricultural production; using renewable energy; creating ecologically sustainable infrastructure; improving water resource management; and improving waste and land resource management. It is essential to record and control the generation, transportation, decontamination, recycling, and disposal of all industrial, medical, veterinary, agricultural, and other types of waste.

Funding problems

Global challenges such as pandemics, climate change, and the biodiversity crisis require a solid financial and multilateral system (15). However, it should also be noted that Georgia, as a low-income developing country, needs more fiscal capacity to finance emergency response and investment-based recovery processes following the SDGs. It needs more access to market financial resources due to low market creditworthiness.

Commercial banks' commercial policy for financing sectors is based mainly on the risks of production and sale of products in the industry. Agriculture is the riskiest and most vulnerable of them all. This is also confirmed by the commercial loans granted to him. According to the National Bank of Georgia data, loans issued in agriculture, forestry, and fishing make up only 5.1 percent of the loan portfolio (2022), which is one of the lowest indicators compared to financing other sectors.

Commercial banks' financing portfolios need to consider the priorities defined by the sustainable development goals. Here we note that the need for more experts in agriculture and environmental protection in financial organizations significantly reduces the feasibility of using green finance.

The National Bank of Georgia studies the impact of environmental and climatic conditions on the finances of companies in Georgia. It investigates changes in credit conditions by providing information

on current and future lending trends from high-level banking sector managers and by determining changes in loan demand and interest and non-interest lending conditions and the factors causing these changes.³

The issue of green finance in agriculture is one of the main directions of World Bank research. In one of his studies, along with traditional barriers (access to loans, lack of long-term loans, etc.), the three main obstacles to lending for agriculture are identified: (1) inadequate enabling environments; (2) a lack of capacity to manage exposure to specific agricultural risks; and (3) high transaction costs. It is mentioned in the study that climate finance can act as a catalyst to (1) unlock additional sources of finance, specifically private capital; (2) tighten the links between FIs and smallholder farmers and SMEs; and (3) provide technical assistance to build the capacities of everyone involved in the financial ecosystem (9, p.5).

Various studies have reviewed strategies for increasing green financing, how to make green investments profitable, how to promote green finance using technology and policy, the role of regulators and financial institutions in the green finance agenda, and the challenges of green finance. Challenges such as lack of awareness of green finance, lack of policy coordination, inconsistent policies, and lack of beneficial incentives for investors and financial institutions willing to invest in climate change mitigation are highlighted (19). Also, researchers pay attention to value chain growth management in financing issues, financing models, etc. (6). In Georgia, research is being conducted toward promoting small and medium-sized enterprises (10).

About the research approach.

Our research question addresses how the vulnerability of industries to environmental risks affects their lending by the financial sector.

Our calculations are based on a methodology in which lending risks are determined by the dimensions of very acute, high-risk, and vulnerable-risk loans. This approach resembles a heat map (heatmap) methodology (2, p.14-18). Five sectors are compared: energy, agriculture, construction, industry, transport, and communication and the concept is taken as a priori, according to which the share of loans should reflect the riskiness of the sectors, including the environment. This concept has found quite a lot of space in the scientific literature (8; 11; 16). We compared the share of issued loans in total assets with the sector's output (GDP). On the other hand, it is considered that different interest rates according to sectors should reflect financial institutions' attitudes toward the sectors' riskiness. A high-interest rate demonstrates the riskiness of the industry.⁴

³ The risk radar proposed by the National Bank of Georgia includes three parts: 1. Physical climate risks, which can be acute and chronic, are assessed with a maximum of 2.8 points. 2. Transit risks based on the regulatory environment, economic impact, technological changes and consumer behaviors are rated at 2.9 points, while other economic, social

and governance risks are rated at 1.3 points, where 0-3 is insignificant, 4-5 is vulnerable, 6-7 high and 8-10 is critical. Through the questionnaire, the respondents' perceptions are quantitatively evaluated from -0 to 100, where 100 indicates a significant improvement in trend.

⁴ Various risks are meant, including marketing ones.

Loans taken by companies by industry⁵

	Share of loans in total loans (2003-2022)*	Interest rate of loans (2003-2022)	Share of the sector in GDP (2010-2022)	Share of loans in GDP	Real growth rate of the industry 2010-2022 (average, previous year = 100)	ratio of the share of loans to the share of the industry	Labor productivity (per one employee, (20 year average)
Agriculture	1.7 (1.8)	13.95 (13.4)	7.7	0,22	3,1	2.9	66840
Industry	12.7 (23.3)	14.4 (12.3)	12,7 **	1	11.5	7.9	140385
Construction	10,9 (9.9)	14,6 (13)	5.9	1,8	4.2	27.1	141906
Transport Communication	3,2 (3.1)	15,8 (12.5)	8.2	0,4	12.2	4.9	78875 (Information and Communication)
Financial intermediation	14,5 (3.3)	11,7 (11.9)	5.1	2,8	9.2	54.9	-

Source: The author's calculations are based on the data of the National Bank of Georgia and the National Statistical Service of Georgia.

• The data in brackets are loans issued in foreign currency.

** Includes mining and processing industries, electricity, gas, steam, air conditioning, water supply, sewage, waste management and decontamination.

Graph 3

Source: National Bank of Georgia, National Statistics Service of Georgia.

Commercial banks' most preferred field of financing is financial intermediation, the share of which is the highest in loans. Agriculture is the highest-risk sector, most exposed to physical and transient climate risks. In turn, it has an increased contribution to climate change, thus contributing to mitigating these risks. It has the lowest share of loans.

Construction is a high-risk sector exposed to physical and transient climate risks and is highly affected by climate, but despite this, its share of loans is very high.

It has high labor productivity in industry, which in the financial sector creates advantages for their financing.

It should also be taken into account that the average loan rate in these years was 14.3 percent in GEL and 12.4 percent in dollars. The different levels of profitability of the industries affected the attractiveness of loans and their lending.

Transport and industry sectors are generally high-risk due to climate change but are financed differently by financial institutions. Agriculture and construction

⁵ The industries are defined by the standard methodology of NACE.Rev2, which is used by the National Statistics Service of Georgia, and the statistics of loans are produced by the National Bank of Georgia, which started using NACE.Rev2 only in 2022, which is why these industries do not comply with the standard updated by the Statistics Service. Accordingly, the financial data is made only from a sectoral perspective. However, defining loans by sector may not provide an accurate representation of the assessment of the different vulnerability of sub-sectors to climate change.

growth rates are similarly lower than the national average of 5.6 percent. However, the range of growth rates in construction is more extensive (from -7 to 22 percent), which indicates its unstable nature.⁶ Lending in different years was independent of climate impact assessments but based on the industry's cyclical nature.

Final note

Although this approach could be better and involves many limiting circumstances, it should be assumed that overall, climate impacts were not given a significant role in financing. Only in agriculture, where labor productivity is very low, and vulnerability is high, did climate impacts on sector performance indirectly affect lending decisions by financial institutions.

Financial institutions' consideration of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors, including climate-related risks, is a critical part of sustainable financing of companies and the state, where environmental performance and consideration of climate impacts in financial and credit activities are essential factors for developing green funding.

The role of stakeholders in the development of financing schemes is excellent. The state, civil society, local communities, associations, etc., are mainly interested in sustainable development. Each of them, within the scope of their authority, can contribute to raising awareness about the financing of sustainable development, eliminating barriers hindering the growth of value, and strengthening stability.

The state promotes green entrepreneurship, economical use of resources, and nature protection activities through significant institutional changes and programs. Today, enterprises receive only "soft" support from the state in segmented areas. Other effective forms of support, such as tax incentives for green entrepreneurship, are effective in environmental activities and are aimed at forming socially responsible enterprises.

To ensure sustainable development, business partnerships are an excellent guarantee to implement financing and strengthen financial flows from one value chain to another, making the entire chain attractive to financial institutions. Creating a shared space between financial institutions and agents involved in value growth, where all business entities participate, united by an interconnected value chain and social responsibility to each other and society, is a way to reduce the risks of entrepreneurs and intensify financial flows.

Firms face different resistance when participating in global market because enterprises must assess the potential market or know the quality and standard requirements. To enter the global markets, it is necessary not only to improve their production methods but also their management and focus on environmentally friendly products and the rational use of natural resources. It is possible to give the enterprise an additional competitive asset if they are focused on informing the public about their responsible attitude towards nature and producing environmentally friendly

products. Enterprises need help to do this, and global suppliers and manufacturers are reluctant to think about such issues. Therefore, targeted cooperation with industry associations, government agencies, and civil society will enable entrepreneurs to establish a new place in the global value chain through extensive media use.

The sectors' vulnerability can be overcome by the government's introduction of institutional mechanisms, partnership relations, and joint efforts between private firms. In the development strategy of green entrepreneurship and financing provision, the government has an institutional role: by establishing tax incentives or tax exemptions to encourage green investments; by introducing solid and long-lasting state programs promoting green business; through constant dialogue with enterprises and potential investors regarding the issuance of green loans; and by forming a risk insurance and guarantee system for them. Norms that would significantly simplify access to credit and increase the credit security system for green entrepreneurs could be based on both direct lending and trust loans between entities involved in the value growth process, the terms of which would be based on a preferential guarantee system for green financing.

Ensuring a green economy refers to changes in both production and consumption models. It is also essential to increase the awareness of financial institutions about the need to finance the green economy. Instead of focusing on short-term benefits, it will be possible to provide long-term sustainable benefits if environmental activities are written in" as one of the conditions for determining their portfolio.

The support of international donors is necessary for institution-building and conducting reforms. The primary role of their activity is to support coordination between business groups and participate in the implementation of green projects.

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